

ISic4335

I.Sicily inscription 4335

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

dedication (?)

Material**Object**

tabula

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Syracusae

Place of origin (modern)

Siracusa

Provenance

Catacomb of S. Giovanni (in re-use?)

Coordinates**Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Siracusa, Museo Archeologico
Regionale Paolo Orsi

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

Bibliography

1923-. Supplementum epigraphicum graecum. *Supplementum epigraphicum graecum*. At 61.0758

Orsi, P. 1895. Insigne epigrafe del cimitero di S. Giovanni in Siracusa. *Römische Quartalschrift für christliche Alterthumskunde und für Kirchengeschichte*. 9: 299-308. At 494 no.192

Wessel, C. 1989. Inscriptiones Graecae Christianae Veteres Occidentis. *Inscriptiones Christianae Italiae*. Bari. At 124

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